

1 **Activation of HERC6 by HPV type 122 E6/E7.**

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6 We demonstrate here selective activation of the E3 ubiquitin ligase *Herc6* by the beta genus HPV type 122
7 E6/E7 oncogenes.

8 Citations

9 1. Oudshoorn, D., van Boheemen, S., Sánchez-Aparicio, M.T., Rajsbaum, R., García-Sastre, A. and
10 Versteeg, G.A., 2012. HERC6 is the main E3 ligase for global ISG15 conjugation in mouse cells. *PLoS*
11 *one*, 7(1), p.e29870.

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